

**ASSESSMENT OF POLITICAL, SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC POLICIES
OF GOVERNOR HERBERT STANLEY IN NORTHERN RHODESIA-
1924-27**

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***Abstract.** Colonial rule was the period weaker nations were dominated by militarily superior nations. This study was intended to review the historiography of Zambia's colonial rule from 1924-27. The study was focused on the establishment of direct British Colonial rule in the region. This study assessed the works of the first governor of Northern Rhodesia from 1924 to 1927. The study argued that the environment in which one grows up has influence on the later lifestyle such a person adopts. It further argued that Governor Herbert Stanley was not the best option for the first governor if the British premises of creating a multiracial nation in Northern Rhodesia were to become a reality. The period of Governor Herbert Stanley was characterised with physical separation of races. Youths were separated into Boy Scouts and Girl Guides for children of European origin and Pathfinders were children of the natives. This study argued that the separation was thought and meant to perpetuate the separation that had existed in Southern Rhodesia and South Africa. Governor Herbert Stanley went on to physically*

separate elderly people. The separation was done through the creation of the Native Reserves. Reserves were created as a way of moving natives from their productive lands and create room for the settlement of European Capitalist settlers in productive lands. The granting of Freehold Land Tenure was argued to be a sign that Governor Herbert Stanley intended to permanently deprive natives the available source of livelihood, which was land.

This study made use of internet sources, PhD and Ma-theses in the library at University of Zambia, and the repository documents online. Data was also gleaned from the National Archives of Zambia. Triangulation method was employed to meet the expectations of the study that dealt with both quantitative and qualitative data.

Keywords: *Governor, natives, settlers, native reserves, multiracial*

Introduction. This chapter defines the formal genesis of political hegemony found in Zambia (Phiri, 2001:224). Gann (1965:161) argued that Northern Rhodesia was seen by European capitalists of Southern Rhodesia as a source of labor and a potential hub of mining enterprises. Despite the discouragements in the early days of settlers in Northern Rhodesia, the prosperity of mining remained unshaken; there was still hope of a miracle that would lead to the discovery of Gold in lands north of Southern Rhodesia (O’Callaghan, 1997:249-50). This chapter discusses the birth of Northern Rhodesia’s protectorate status. The chapter also takes interest in the policies on the economic, social, and political spheres implemented by Governor Stanley. Gann (1958:10-11) contended that Northern Rhodesia 1924 was made an official Crown Protectorate of Great Britain and it was administered through Executive and Legislative Councils. The executive and the Legislative Council were both

presided over by the Governor, (Kaplan, et al. 1969:45). The chapter further assessed the works of Governor Herbert Stanley on racial separateness as seen in areas of land tenure, education, and the programs for the native youths.

Sir Herbert Stanley's Early Life - 1872-1918

Stanley was born in England on 25th July 1872. He was educated at Eton College and Balliol College in Oxford (*Times*). Eton College enrolled learners aged from 13 to 18 and was an independent boarding school for boys in the town of Eton, near Windsor in Berkshire, England. It was an old school that was founded in 1440 by King Henry VI as "Kynge's College of Our Lady of Eton beside Windsor", (Tim, 2001:10) as a sister institution to King's College, Cambridge, making it the 18th-oldest Headmasters' and Headmistresses' Conference school. Neville (1911) argued that Eton's history and influence have made it one of the most prestigious schools in the world. Following the public school tradition, Eton became a full boarding school, which meant pupils lived at the school seven days a week, (McConnell, 1967) and it is one of only five remaining single-sex boys', boarding only independent senior schools in the United Kingdom. The motto of the school was *Flourish Eton*. The school was renowned for its corporal punishment which was only abolished in the 1980s. As a result of its good morals, the school was the nursery grounds for Oxford University.

The school was headed by a provost and fellows (board of governors) who appointed the headmaster. It contained 25 boys' houses each headed by a housemaster, selected from the more senior members of the teaching staff, which numbered some 155 (McConnell, 1967:89). Almost all of the school's pupils go on to universities, about a third of them to Oxford or Cambridge (Tim, 2001:58).

Source: Free encyclopedia. Retrieved on 2/02/2021

Figure 1. Eton College

As a young soldier who lived in South Africa, Herbert Stanley was aware of the rivalry that existed between the British peoples of South Africa and the Boers of that country as shown by the War of 1899-1902 (Hussey, 1963). Hussey argues that British soldiers under the command of Sir Redvers Buller in the war against Boers of Transvaal in 1899-1902, started badly though they ended in victory after reinforcements from India and Australia. During World War I (WWI), Herbert Stanley was based in South Africa. The ‘Pulsating’ beauty that resonated from Reniera, made Herbert Stanley decide to marry. He married Reniera Cloete who was from a leading Cape Town family in 1918. Reniera was held to be one of the most beautiful women of the century in any country in the world even without holding a beauty contest according to Halugalle (1963:194).

The background showed that racism was real in most African countries. Devonshire's report dealing with the status of the Indians in Kenya revealed as early as 1923 that Europeans had difficulties living with other races (NAZ, July 1923). The report further stated that in 1913, a distinguished sanitation expert, Professor (called Sir William) Simpson, furnished a report on sanitary matters in Kenya, in which he advocated for a system of racial segregation, both in the residential and in the commercial areas of large towns.

Herbert Stanley's public works started in Foreign Service in Dresden and Cobourg. He worked as a Resident Commissioner for Southern and Northern Rhodesia (Wood, 2005). In these early days, there was a desire amongst the early settlers to create a country that "mirrored the image of Britain in terms of its demographic composition and economic health (Maravanyika and Huijzenveld, 2010: 18-33). It was this desire which led to the development of a settler identity that promoted the superiority of British settlers (over indigenous Africans). The majority of the settlers were British-born or British South African. As such, they promoted their home country's brand of civilization (Bonnello, 2010: 341-361). Resident Commissioner Stanley had the obligation of supporting ordinances that the British Monarch had passed regarding the affairs of its nationals in Africa. For instance, Mason (1955: 240-41) reveals the sentiments of white women in Northern Rhodesia who seemed to have been the bulwarks of racial segregation. He quotes the secretary of the Northern Rhodesia Women's League who stated that it is not generally known that in 1903 (before women of Rhodesia had the right to vote) the Immorality Suppression Ordinance was passed, making it a criminal offence for a white woman to cohabit with a native, while the reverse relationship between white men and native women continues to remain outside the cognizance of the law.

Governor Sir Herbert Stanley in Northern Rhodesia, 1924-27

The office of the Governor of Northern Rhodesia was established on 20 February 1924, when the Northern Rhodesia Order-in-Council, 1924 was adopted. The order-in-council of 1924 provided that, there shall be a Governor and Commander in Chief in and over Northern Rhodesia. Therefore, the Northern Rhodesia Order-in-Council of 1924 No. 324 came into operation on 1st April 1924 and it revoked the 1911 Order-in-Council. The British South Africa Chartered Company's administration of Northern Rhodesia ceased and the Governor was put in charge of the territory on His Majesty's behalf (Colonial Report, 1933). Sir Herbert Stanley took the oath as the first Governor and Commander-in-Chief of Northern Rhodesia on 1st April 1924 and became Sir Herbert Stanley (Colonial Report, 1926). Moder and Zingel (2019:33) argued that in 1924; a centralized administration for Northern Rhodesia was set up by Sir Herbert Stanley, who had previously served in Southern Rhodesia and South Africa, after being appointed as the first Governor. He had the Executive Council that had five members (Colonial Report, 1935). The Executive Council made up of civil servants such as the Chief Secretary, the Attorney General, the Treasurer, the Secretary for Native Affairs, and the Director of the Medical Services, was the advisor to the Governor. There was a provision for the governor to include extraordinary members on special occasions. Sir Herbert Stanley believed that Northern Rhodesia should be developed as a "Whiteman's Country". Under his guidance, the country sought to encourage more European settlements (Moder and Zingel, 2019:34).

Phiri (2001:19) praised Sir Herbert Stanley as a "Saviour" of natives of Northern Rhodesia as his rule showed that he was sympathetic to them as deduced in the act of reducing taxes in 1925 and the setting up of the land commissions that prevented some natives from being removed from their native land. The details on

the creation of Native Reserves, speaks to the contrary of Phri's praise for Governor Herbert Stanley. As the first governor, Sir Herbert Stanley was expected to set the base unite of races. He found two classes of settlers in particular.

The two classes of Europeans were the Afrikaners and those of British origin. The economic status of the two classes of people of European origin in Northern Rhodesia was different. Wallenstein (2010) used an economic basis to understand global inequality. Core nations were termed developed while the peripherals were known as undeveloped and backward. World system theory, like dependency theory, suggests that wealthy countries benefited from other countries and exploited those countries' citizens. To Wallenstein, the way a nation integrates into a Capitalist world system determines what economic development takes place in that country. Northern Rhodesia at that time did not have an industry for manufacturing. The mining industries available were all specialized in the extraction of raw materials that would be exported at forty-five percent pure as concentrate. The farming industry equally produced raw materials. That made the economy of the region by 1924 undeveloped.

Governor Herbert started his rule at the time Africans' frustration and anger at being mistreated was visible through their actions. Ranger underscored that African acquiescence was not to be taken for granted after World War One (WWI) in Northern Rhodesia. At the end of that war, there had been widespread defiance of the administration in North-eastern Rhodesia (Ranger, 2004:349).

These acts of defiance were so wide that Judge MacDonnell had to be asked to inquire into the causes of the same. There was a slight drift from the usual African who did not know how to question the action done by a white person. The British authority in Africa wanted to establish the genesis of such acts from Africans. Judge MacDonnell took time to gather information to establish the cause

of the defiance. The findings of Judge MacDonnell, after undertaking his inquiries into the cause of the disturbances were conveyed. He discovered that Africans were not happy with the status quo. Their tradition of not asking the reason for the action was slowly being replaced with that one that demanded cause.

The report to the administrator on 5th May 1919 revealed that there was evidence which showed that the old words such as obedience to elders, headmen, and chiefs, and obedience to the Boma, had lost their meaning (McConnell, 1979:58). In the report given, it was clear that MacDonnell was reporting the loss of loyalty to people of authority as the cause of the disturbances. The report showed that the respect or fear Africans had towards their superiors was eroding. Words such as Boma, and Bwana, were not carrying the authority they had always carried.

To claim the lost glory, Governor Sir Herbert Stanley wanted to make his entry into Northern Rhodesia grandiose to register to the people of the protectorate that the Company rule was over and that the new ruler was directly connected to the most powerful Monarchy in the world. He wanted people to have respect for the throne of HRH and that of the Governor who represented His Royal Highness. Ranger argues that Stanley was sympathetic to the aspirations of white settlers, but only if they were of British stock (Maravanyika and Huijzenveld, 2010:33). It can be deduced that the attitude of Sir Herbert Stanley towards the Afrikaners showed that he was indifferent to them. Ranger clarifies that ardently those who were loyal to the Crown were looked upon differently from those who were not (Ranger, 2004:350). As earlier mentioned, the situation in Northern Rhodesia was already ripe for racial segregation. Except for this time, the grounds for separation were unique.

Afrikaner farmers had settled around Lusaka. These were whites who did not grow up with the knowledge of asking *God to save the King*. Hence, their children did not know *the "God Save the King"*, recitation. The recitations by the children were just a way of allowing children to grow up with the love of the King (Roberts, 1978:55-61). Governor Stanley was faced with the task of inculcating values in young ones of praying for the well-being of their leaders. In addition, Governor Herbert Stanley had the other task of changing settlers that observed Rhodesia feast days. He had to help such English-speaking whites who most of them had settled around the Fort Jameson area stop observing Rhodes Feast Days and learn to observe Empire Day which was important.

Visit of Prince of Wales to Northern Rhodesia-1925

Sapira comments that the visit of the Prince of Wales in 1925 had the chief purposes of promoting unity amongst the "white races," raising the morale of the "British element," and reconciling Afrikaners to the imperial connection while the last of the Prince's dominion tours was regarded as the most politically challenging and portentous (Sapira, 2018:110-11). Spanning the first half of the 1920s, these modern royal signs of progress took the Prince to North America, the Antipodes, the Pacific, and India, and together with visits to areas of high unemployment, poverty, and deprivation in the UK in the 1930s, were crucial to the monarchy's popularity. The brainchild of both Prime Minister David Lloyd George and King George V, the empire tours were intended to furnish a meaningful role for the Prince of Wales following his war service, to thank the empire for its wartime contribution, and to help resolve the crisis presented to the imperial crown in the form of post-war nationalist dissent and the dominions' search for "status" and greater autonomy within the empire (Sapira, 2018:111).

The authorities at home and the dominion capitals hoped that the presence of a representative of the crown would persuade skeptics, cultural nationalists, and separatists that not only were the crown more than a decorative “feudal anachronism,” but that it was a pivot and vital symbol of imperial unity (Godfrey, 1998:182). When completed, the dominion tours were hailed as a signal of achievement in this regard, even if some intellectuals regarded them as propaganda unparalleled in the world’s history (Aronson, 1975:82).

Northern Rhodesia too had Afrikaners, British settlers, Asiatic peoples, and Natives who had taken part in the struggle against the Central Powers from 1914 to 1918. Prince was needed to reconcile them. The preparations for the visit of the Prince of Wales to Northern Rhodesia began in 1924 and revealed a lot about the Governor of Northern Rhodesia. He showed traits of an egocentric person. Egocentric is defined as thinking only about yourself and not about others (Turnbull, 2010:410).

Sir Herbert Stanley disclosed to the Prince of Wales that there was nothing much to choose between any of the African chiefs in the matter of dignity and importance. He generally spoke that none were likely to look impressive apart from the Lozi people who had special dressing for their ceremony (NAZ, 1925). Sardonicly, Governor Stanley informed the Prince of Wales that even the White population in the area could not attend formal occasions as most of them did not have evening clothes and could not afford to provide for themselves with some fancy dress.

To inculcate these norms, Governor Herbert Stanley came up with his *modus operandi*. He started with the young minds of European children in his country. He revived among White children in Northern Rhodesia the ideals of the Boy Scouts

and Girl Guides. To appreciate the significance of these two movements it called for delving into how these movements started in the world.

History of Boy Scout and Girl Guide Movements in Europe

The Boy Scout and Girl Guide movements in Europe and America have a long and rich history. The movements began with Lieutenant General Robert Stephenson Smyth Baden-Powell who worked closely with his sister and thus they have been accredited with the birth of these two movements. Though Lieutenant General Robert Stephenson Smyth Baden-Powell accepted this accolade, he did not take pride in the praise. He reluctantly attributed it to his upbringing at a farmhouse where he liked outdoor activities (James and Peter, 1932:138). He hunted with traps to catch rodents and birds.

Lieutenant General Robert Stephenson Smyth Baden-Powell, 1st Baron Baden-Powell was born on 22nd February 1857 and died on 8th January 1941. He was a British Army officer, writer, and first Chief Scout of the worldwide Scout Movement. He had a co-founder, his sister Agnes Baden-Powell. Deacon (2016) underscored that Robert Baden-Powell authored the first editions of *The Seminal work on Scouting for Boys*, which was an inspiration for the Scout Movement. He went and served in South Africa during the Mafeking war with the Boers. Bradfield narrated that three years later, in South Africa during the Second Boer War, Baden-Powell was besieged in the small town of Mafekeng by a much larger Boer army. Bradfield (1970) contends that the Mafekeng Cadet Corps was a group of youths that supported the troops by carrying messages, which freed the men for military duties and kept the boys occupied during the long siege. The Cadet Corps performed well, helping in the defence of the town (1899–1900), and were one of the many factors that inspired Baden-Powell to form the Scouting movement.

In August 1907 he held a camp on Brownsea Island to test out his ideas. About twenty boys attended. Of those who attended, eight were from local Boys' Brigade companies, and about twelve were public schoolboys. The Scouts in attendance were mostly sons of Powell's friends.

Boys and girls spontaneously formed Scout troops and the Scouting Movement had inadvertently started, first as a national, and soon an international phenomenon (Mills, 2011:537-56). A rally of Scouts was held at Crystal Palace in London in 1909, at which Baden-Powell met some of the first Girl Scouts. The Girl Guides were subsequently formed in 1910 under the auspices of Baden-Powell's sister, Agnes Baden-Powell (Mills, 2013:120-134).

Sir Herbert Stanley knowing well his cards adopted the ideals of the Scout Movement and Girl Guides and taught the lads and girls upon assuming office in Northern Rhodesia. Ranger (2004:352) argued that Governor Stanley proceeded to inform leading officials, churchmen, and settlers that the Scouts movement was rapidly spreading in the Empire. Ranger further argues that Stanley disclosed the areas he had prepared the Scouts such as the reciting of the Oath and knowledge of thrift, chivalry, patriotism, and the rules of health. The investiture ceremony was held on the 1st Day of November 1924 when six boys as Tenderfoots were presented to the Governor at the Government House in Livingstone. The Oath was, "Can I trust you, on your honor, to do your best; to be loyal to God and the King; to do good turns to other people, to keep Scout Law?"(www.scouting.org). The oath Governor Herbert administered had three most important features which he wanted newly invested Scouts to know. They were God in heaven and the King on Earth in Great Britain, and the people of British origin.

The Scouts Academy held that every Scout was expected to live with the twelve principles which were, trustworthy, loyal, brave, helpful, friendly,

courteous, kind, obedient, cheerful, thrifty, clean, and reverent. The oath Governor Stanley administered to the first Scouts showed his intent regarding what young minds were to focus their reverence on (Ranger, 2004:353). Governor was set to erase all memories of Company rule. The challenge was that while white children were receiving such lessons, native children were not included in the Boy Scout and Girl Guide movements. They were made to belong to their movement. The native boys belonged to Pathfinder Movement which was very distinct in all ways. Their uniforms and even the Oath were to be different from those of the Scout Movement. Ranger (2004:367) noted how the Pathfinder movement was organized in Transvaal and later in Northern Rhodesia. He wrote;

The Pathfinder Movement consists of some 2000 boys, but they do not at any time parade with Scouts, nor do they do anything which might confuse the two Movements. It has been necessary to keep a very close watch on the method of dress and the system employed, so there would be no over-lapping. When the Pathfinder Scouts were constituted in Northern Rhodesia, their structure and regulations were modeled on those of the movement in Southern Rhodesia. The movement was defined as being for according to boys of Bantu origin the benefits of the principles and practices of the Scout Movement. Their Oath was, 'A Pathfinder Scout is loyal to the King, to the King's representative in Northern Rhodesia, to his Chief, and Tribal Elders, to his officers and those under him.

Reflecting on the value of the oath, it must be known that the Oath is a solemn promise to fulfill a pledge, often calling upon God as a witness. It can be noted that Governor Stanley was quick to point out that loyalty was to God and the King when he addressed the white children. In the Pathfinder movement, the highest authority was the King. Since King worked with people he delegated authority to, the Governor being such an individual, he needed to be respected and

recognized as the supreme authority in a vast land of Northern Rhodesia. Nicolaas (1991:81-82) argued that most African youths including Kenneth Kaunda were trained in the duties of Pathfinders in schools. Other than social issues, Governor Stanley carried out political duties in Northern Rhodesia.

Sir Herbert Stanley being the first Governor of Northern Rhodesia had the duty of defining the political institutions of his Protectorate. For administrative purposes, the territory of Northern Rhodesia was divided into nine provinces, each of which was under a Provincial Commissioner responsible for his province to the Governor (Colonial Report, 1933). The provinces were divided into districts under the charge of District Officers who responded to the Provincial Commissioners. Governor Herbert Stanley was the founding Governor who shaped the political divisions of Zambia. Important to note is that the identities of the provinces have changed. There were names such as Barotse, Awemba, Kafue, Batoka, Luangwa, Kasempa, East-luangwa, Tanganyika and Mweru-luapula (NAZ/SEC, 1929). There was the Central Government where the Governor was in-charge. As the President of the Legco, the Governor chaired its debates (Wright, 1945:122-30). Wright further argued that the Governor of Northern Rhodesia, in his legislative as well as executive capacity, was bound to obey the directives of the Secretary of State, whether or not they conformed to his personal views. Therefore, Governor Stanley in function had the role of the President of the Legco and that of the Executive combined in himself (Davidson, 1946:138).

Governor Herbert Stanley used the visit of the Prince of Wales to raise levels in the profile of both the British Monarchy and his own. The Governor did not want to lose such an opportunity to assert glory arising from the sluggish performance of Great Britain in the First World War. Before the Prince of Wales arrived in Northern Rhodesia, special attention to his appearance was emphasised.

The Prince arrived in Northern Rhodesia in May 1925 and was asked to look sophisticated in his dressing (Ranger, 2004:367-69). Ranger further argued that Sir Herbert Stanley himself was mostly clad in white clothes to look complicated. When the Prince of Wales arrived in Northern Rhodesia in May 1925, he inspected a guard of honor staged by the Scouts. He also met native leaders and commissioned some projects in Broken Hill. The report stated that subsequently, His Royal Highness motored the 40 miles that separate Broken Hill from Mulungushi, where, by turning a small wheel made from the mine zinc, the Prince freed the water from the dam and allowed it to enter the pressure pipes conveying power to the dynamos 1,200 feet below, and thus formally opened the first electric power scheme in Northern Rhodesia (Colonial Reports, 1927). The visit of the Prince of Wales to Northern Rhodesia had activities to do with the Native Authorities, and settlers as well as the commissioning of some government projects in Broken Hill.

Fiscal Policy and the Land Tenure in Northern Rhodesia- 1924-27

Governor Herbert Stanley had a fiscal policy that was mainly based on the following sources of revenue; the customs on the imported goods. His exported countries in this area included the Union of South Africa, Southern Rhodesia, the United Kingdom, the rest of the British Empire, and foreign currencies (Colonial Reports, 1926). The other sources of revenue included in the report were the licenses, excise, and internal revenue, fees of court, post office, rent on government property, interest, miscellaneous, and land sales. These were on a backdrop of the expenditure based on the areas such as the government office, secretariat, European education, printing and stationery, District Administration, Treasury, Commissioner of Taxes, Customs, Post and Telegraphs, Audit Office, Judiciary,

legal and prisons Department, Transport and Supply, survey, Northern Rhodesia Police, Mines, and Public works, public works Recurrent, Public works Extraordinary, Percentage of tax payable to Barotseland, miscellaneous services, and the pensions and gratuities.

Table 1: Northern Rhodesia Revenue 1924-25

S/N	DESCRIPTION	£	S	d
1	Customs	72 720	16	8
2	Licenses, excise and internal revenue	162 395	11	7
3	Fees of court	27 914	12	10
4	Post office	18 121	4	11
5	Rent on government property	11 486	2	6
6	Interests	715	4	4
7	Miscellaneous	3 635	3	10
8	Land sales	12 805	18	11
9	Total	309 794	15	7

Source: Adapted from Colonial Report, 1926, p. 7.

The fiscal policy for Governor Herbert Stanley in the period 1924-25 taxed natives though it did not provide the expense for the natives. The only native that received from the government was the tax payable to Barotseland. Expense on the native education was met by the missionaries. Governor Herbert Stanley had spent the greater part of his early life and early career in Southern Africa and was well known for his strong pro-settler views. His ideas on the role that settlers could play in the development of the territory were to have a great influence on the Administration of the land policy (Dixon-Fyle, 1976:57). Governor Herbert

Stanley and his administrators were very sure that more settlers would migrate to Northern Rhodesia. Understanding the task at hand, Governor Stanley talked the Colonial Office into agreeing with his view of preparing for those expected migrants. Hence, between 1924 and 1927 Native Reserves Commissions were set up in the territory to examine the land situation in all three areas where settlers had taken up residence. The Commission which examined the land situated along the line of rail was set up in July 1926. The members were P.J. MacDonnell, a Judge of the High Court, J. Moffat Thomson, a District Commissioner who later became Secretary for Native Affairs, and H.P. Hart, a local farmer (Brown, 2004:83; Mvunga, 1980:16). The Commission sat in the Mazabuka District in October 1926 and it heard evidence from white settlers, mainly farmers, and local chiefs. The farmers were divided on the question of whether reserves were necessary or not. The proponents of Reserves argued that the move would serve settlers the trouble of fencing. Fencing was seen as the way to avoid cattle that belonged to the settlers mixing with the breed of the natives. The strong reason for that move was to reduce the spread of diseases. The Commission established land tenure in respect of the indigenous African population, settlers, and State or Crown. The areas that were surveyed included the East Luangwa District (now Eastern Province) and the Railway Belt (an area that now comprises parts of Southern Province, Lusaka, Central, and Copperbelt Provinces). Chisulo (2016:26) has defined Land tenure as the legal right to own and use the land for personal or communal benefit. Governor Stanley introduced dual land tenure in Northern Rhodesia. They were Crown land held under Freehold Land Tenure and the Customary held as Native Reserve.

In justifying the creation of Native Reserves, Logan (1939:53-55) argued that a key objective of British administrators was to produce African subjects with 'modern' habits of progress by inculcating certain forms of economic, ecological,

and political rationality. He further contended that Native Reserves aimed to help the Africans build up and maintain a healthy mind and a healthy body to encourage them to think out schemes for their improvement. Logan added that Africa's economic growth and political growth were to be realized when they are separated from the settlers. Logan deliberately ignored the fact that even in the Native Reserves; political issues were still a preserve of the Governor. In essence, the creation of Native Reserves was a well-thought plan to permanently deprive fertile land of the locals who initially were able to feed themselves without depending on being hired laborers. Governor Stanley was ready to continue on the trajectory started by the Company. His role was to legalize the separation by creating real reserves for natives. Governor Stanley went ahead to constitute a third Commission.

Kalikiti (2013:129) argued that a third Commission led by Judge J. Moffat Thompson dealt with Tanganyika District (now Northern and parts of Muchinga Provinces. Then referred to Northern Province) was appointed in 1927. These Commissions apportioned land into European land (alienated) as Crown Land and African Land (unalienated) represented by Native Reserves. The base for the indirect rule was set by the first Governor as Africans were on their own away from settlers. Africans who were on land that was marked as Crown land were set to be moved into the Reserves without compensation for the loss they suffered. Palmer laments that all the Reserves set up during this period did not equal in extent to the land set aside as Barotseland Reserve based on the British South Africa Company agreements (Palmer, NAZ:64).

It should be noted that there was some sort of continuation in terms of land rights on the Crown land under Sir Herbert Stanley from the British South Africa Company. Land tenure under BSAC was Freehold on alienated land. Sir Herbert

Stanley did not see any need to change this law. Freehold tenure was a landholding system where a person owned a right of beneficial occupation of the land that might devolve up to his successors *ad infinitum*, but could only come to an end on the failure of successors to maintain the holding rights (Kakoma, 1987:17). This meant that a landholder enjoying that system of land tenure, held land *indefinitely* unless the land was escheated to the Crown. Thus, the Crown only had a reversionary interest in the land where there was a total failure of successors to inherit the title. To settlers, this law was very good as it gave them much-needed security. Governor Stanley granted them their wish during his tenure of office. They had no fear of being left landless once the land was granted to them. The government could only claim back the land where it was clear that no one would claim back the land when the holder was no longer using the piece of land in question. This law was repugnant to good land management ethos by later Governors as it encouraged absent Land Lords.

The creation of Native Reserves had far-reaching consequences. Africans were forced systematically into being proletariats. Without even consulting them, capitalism was to be the rule of economic activities henceforth. Capitalism required for its functioning, the creation of a working class, who can be the proletariat, to serve the privileged. The proletariat was initially produced through “brute force” that alienated producers from the means of production, dispossessing people of their land and other productive assets and thus forcing them to sell their labour to survive (Marx, 1990:915). The best formula to create a want for Africans to seek employment on farms owned by Whites was to grab their only available means of production. This was the birth of survival based on working for others than being the employers they had always been. Talking about the Native Reserves, Perelman argues that the process had two blades. The first blade served

to undermine the ability of the people to provide for themselves. The other blade was a system of stern measures required to keep people from finding alternative survival strategies outside of the system of waged labor (Perelman, 2001: 7-8).

Perelman brought out issues that talked about the intent of the creation of the Native Reserves. Before the creation of the Reserves, Africans were employers and not workers. Their livelihood was supported by the portion of land they had. So the authority had the best land given to people of its kind. The indigenous people were left to occupy lands that were not good for farming and in some areas, not good for Pastoralism. Large areas of the Territory are made impossible for cattle by the presence of tsetse fly (Colonial Reports, 1926). Talk about the principle of the winner takes it all, was well defined in this scenario. Herbert Stanley can be said to have succeeded in his policies of recreating the respect and fear for his Majesty's position and those he delegated power to. Native Reserves were just one method used to entrench racially oriented policies in Northern Rhodesia. People were practically taught to live as tribal groupings. As seen above youths were equally divided as they belonged to either the Boy Scout movement (Europeans) or the Pathfinder Movement (Natives). Attached to land rights was the position of mineral rights in the region. Governor Stanley faced the imaging concern from settlers in Northern Rhodesia. Ndulo (1987) recalls that members of the Legislative Council in Northern Rhodesia contested the ownership of minerals. On 20th July 1927, a motion demanding the investigation of mineral ownership and the legality of the claim was raised by the members of the Legislative Council. The mover of the motion contended that the concessions could not be valid Lewanika was not literate to understand the legal language that was used in the agreement. He also debated that the price for the acquisition of the rights was not commensurate with the value of what was acquired (Debate of Legco, 1927:164).

Governor Herbert Stanley's position on the matter was that of maintaining the status quo. He reminded the Council that the issue of mineral rights was a settled one. He argued that the Colonial Office in 1923 looked into it and a conclusion was then arrived at. Governor Herbert Stanley argued that the Colonial Office recognized the authenticity of the concession signed between the BSAC and natives of Northern Rhodesia (Ndulo, 1987:47-8). Legislative Council Members were asked to avoid raising issues that could invalidate concessions that were entered into and recognized by the Colonial Office. The BSAC in this case was allowed to enjoy the privileges of being in charge of mineral rights as it were before the establishment of Executive and Legco in Northern Rhodesia.

Policy on European and Native Education in Northern Rhodesia, 1924-27.

Radford and his colleagues argued that an education system is a result of decisions made and designs laid down by past and present Governments (UNESCO, 1964:1). That statement remained true for years from the period when Radford and his colleagues wrote about it in their report on the future development of the education system of what was then known as Northern Rhodesia (Kelly, 1991:6). There were separate schools for Natives and Europeans during colonial government. The 1924/5 annual report revealed that there were six Government schools, three farm schools, and one Government-aided school; all, except one, at Fort Jameson, were situated on or near the railway line. Two of the Government schools, those at Kalomo and Mazabuka, had boarding houses attached to them with accommodation for 44 children. Twenty-one teachers were employed in the schools to meet the educational needs of the European children (Colonial Report, 1926). There was a deliberate move to meet the educational needs of the children of the settlers. The colonial annual report argued in clear and certain terms that:

Government activities in this direction have hitherto been confined to the Barotse National School at Mongu, which is financed by the Barotse Trust Fund, and, together with out-schools, is staffed by three Europeans and twenty natives and attended by 782 children; and to a small school in the native location at Livingstone, which is at present attended by forty-two children. Elsewhere the education of natives has been left in the hands of the various Missionary Societies, of which there are fifteen at work in the Territory (Colonial Reports, 1926).

Sir Herbert Stanley promoted an education system that separated Europeans from non-Europeans. A look at the education system that was followed in the region, one was able to draw many similarities with Native Reserves. For instance, the British adaptation of education policy for Africans in Zambia between 1925 and 1964 was trying to follow much of what the Phelps-Stokes Commission to East and Central Africa had suggested (Lewis 1962). Adaptation was defined by one influential member of the Phelps-Stokes Commission, Thomas Jesse Jones, as: Training to meet the everyday needs of native life, to correct the present glaring deficiencies and to strengthen and develop the good points (Jones, 1925:218).

Mukoboto (1978:2-3) argued that the other group emphasized the point that the African educational system must be conditioned by Africa's backwardness and its low standards of living and that the Africans should be trained to become manual workers, artisans, and not sophisticated industrial, technical workers. Such arguments prejudiced the intellectual abilities for natives. Education content for natives was meant to enable them communicate with the master. That gave substandard education to natives. Governor Stanley reported an improvement regarding Native Education in the annual report for the period 1925-26. It was argued that as forecasted in the previous year's report, the Government began in the year under review (1925/26) to take a more active interest in Native Education. A

sub-department of Native Education under the Department of Native Affairs came into being on the 1st of April, 1925 (Colonial Report, 1927).

In supporting the Colonial Annual Report, Nicolaas (1991:76) argued that when Colonial Office took over the government of Northern Rhodesia from the BSAC, it showed that it was more inclined to support the education and medical work that was being done by the mission. In 1925 a sub-department of Native Affairs was established with Geoffrey C. Latham as its Director. The annual report (1927) on the other hand further contained a narration that there were appointments of the Director; an Advisory Board on which missionaries, officials, and settlers were represented. Arguably, this Board had its first meeting in July 1925. Time did not allow Governor H. Stanley remain in power in Northern Rhodesia ad infinitum. His retirement finally came on 25 of July 1927. Upon his retirement, Sir Herbert Stanley settled in Cape Town and was appointed Chief Commissioner of the Boy Scouts of South Africa. He died a widower in a Cape Town nursing home, aged 82 in 1955. He survived by two sons and two daughters.

Conclusion. This study has endeavored to assess the works of the first Governor of Northern Rhodesia covering the period from 1924 to 1927. Governor Herbert Stanley was a well-educated and prepared citizen for public work. This chapter has discussed that Governor Herbert Stanley spent part of his early life before assuming the position of Governor of Northern Rhodesia in South Africa and Southern Rhodesia. The choice of the Colonial Office for the first Governor [Herbert Stanley] made for Northern Rhodesia showed that Colonial Office was interested in escalating racialism in the region. He grew up in the environment that did not respect multiracialism. He was, therefore, not likely to build a multiracial nation in Central Africa as it was espoused. This study has contended that

governors were expected to follow directives Colonial Office would give. It, therefore, notes that Colonial Office was equally not interested in a multiracial nation in Northern Rhodesia.

This chapter has revealed that the proletariat society was started by Governor Stanley in Northern Rhodesia through the creation of the Native Reserves. There was no class of proletariats among natives before the creation of Native Reserves. With the creation of Native Reserves came the class of natives who were employees of the European capitalists. That happened on the backdrop of the family structure of Northern Rhodesia which was not only based on codification that focused on nucleus one but extended members who were identified as family (Simson, 1985). The Reserves and employed labor made extended families to be frowned upon. Racial separateness was entrenched with separation of youths on racial grounds with Scouts/Girl Guides on one hand for European children and the Pathfinders composed of the native children.

References:

1. A, CAB/24/161,(1923). A, The National Archives, July, pp.2-3, part I.
2. Brown T. (2004). Contestation and Corruption: Market Based Land Reform and Local politics in Zambia. Boston: Brill.
3. Bruce John W. and Dorner Peter P. (1985). Agriculture Land Tenure in Zambia: Perspectives, Problems and Opportunities. Wisconsin: Land Tenure Centre.
4. Bwalya Kelvin F. (2018). Zambia Must Prosper. Actualising Zambia's Prayer for Prosperity. Lusaka: DATAAFRIKA.

5. Chisulo A. (2016). “Assessment of Land Policies in Zambia. A Study of Mkushi Farm Block and Adjacent Areas, 1950-2015”, MA Thesis, Zambian Open University.

6. Colonial Report (1933). Annual Report on the Social and Economic Progress of the People of Northern Rhodesia, 1932. London: His Majesty’s Stationery.

7. Colonial Report (1926). Annual Report on the Social and Economic Progress of the People of Northern Rhodesia, 1924-25. London: His Majesty’s Stationery, 1926.

8. Colonial Reports (1926). Annual Reports on the Social and Economic Progress of the People of Northern Rhodesia, 1924-25. London: His Majesty’s Stationary Office, 1926.

9. Colonial Reports (1927). Annual Reports on the Social and Economic Progress of the People of Northern Rhodesia, 1925-26. London: His Majesty’s Stationary.

10. Davidson J.W.,(1946). Northern Rhodesia Legislative Council. London: Faber and Faber.

11. Dixon-Fyle McSamuel Richmond (1976). “Politics and Agrarian Change Among the Plateau Tonga of Northern Rhodesia”, 1924-63, PhD Thesis, University of London.

12. Emmanuel Wallenstein’s World systems Theory Summary. <https://www.boundless.com/sociology/textbook/> , on 2/02/2021.

13. Gann Lewis H. (1958). The Birth of Plural Society: The Development of Northern Rhodesia Under the British South Africa Company. Manchester: Manchester University Press.

14. Gann Louis. H. (1965). A history of Southern Rhodesia: Early days to 1934. London: Chatto and Windus.
15. Hulugalle J. A. H. (1963). British Governors of Ceylon, Associated Newspapers of Ceylon.
16. Hussey W.D. (1963). The British Empire & Commonwealth, 1500-1961. London: Cambridge University Press.
17. Ipenburg A. Nicolaas,(1991). “The Development of Lubwa Mission, Chinsali, Zambia, 1904- 1964”, PhD Thesis, University of London.
18. Jesse Thomas Jones, “The White man’s Burden in Africa,” Current History 23(1925), p.218.
19. Kakoma B. (1987). Ministry of Lands, Ministerial Statement in Parliament, 4th August. Lusaka: Government Printers.
20. Kalikiti W. S. (2013). “Colonial Legacy: Post-Colonial Land Policies, the Rural Masses and the Peri-Urban ‘Poor’ in Zambia 1964-2012,” Journal of Humanities, Special Issue, p.129.
21. Kaplan Irving, et al,(1969). Area Handbook for Zambia. Washington, DC: American University Press.
22. Kelly Michael J.,(1991). Education in a Declining Economy. The Case of Zambia 1975-1985. Washington, DC: World Bank.
23. Lewis L. J. (ed.) (1962). Phelps-Stock Reports on Education in Africa. London: Oxford University Press
24. Logan W. M. (1939). ‘Native Administration in Northern Rhodesia.’ Race, Relations, 6 (3), pp. 53-5.
25. MacDonnell P. to Administrators, 5 May 1919, Cited in Karen E. Fields (1979). “The Ordinary and the Extraordinary in Social Movements”. New York: American Historical Association Conference.

26. Maravanyika S. and Huijzenveld F. D. (2010). 'A failed neo-Britain: Demography and the labour question in colonial Zimbabwe c.1890-1948', *African Nebula*, 1, (1):18-33.

27. Marx Karl (1990). *Capital; A Critique of Political Economy*, volume one. London: Penguin.

28. Mason P. (1955). *The Birth of a Dilemma: The Conquest and Settlement of Rhodesia*. London: Oxford University Press.

29. McConnell J.D.R. (1967). *Eton: How It Works*. London: Faber and Faber.

30. Michael Deacon (2016). *The eccentric world of Robert Baden-Powell*, Telegraph Media Group Ltd. Retrieved on 1st September 2020.

31. Mills Sarah (2013). "An Instruction in good Citizenship: Scouting and the Historical Geographies of Citizenship Education." In *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographer*, 38 (1), pp. 120-134.

32. Mills Sarah,(2011). "Scouting for Girls? Gender and Scout Movement in Britain." In *Gender, Place and Culture*, 18 (4), pp. 537-556.

33. Mlambo A. S. (2000). 'Some are more white than others':Racial chauvinism as a factor in Rhodesian immigration policy, 1890 to 1963", *Zambezia*, 17, (2) pp. 139-160;

34. Moder Karin and Zingel Heribert (eds.) (2019). *Young Zambia between Poverty and Abundant Resources*. Frankfurt: German National Library.

35. Mukobota Sibeso (1978). "The British Adaptation of Education Policy for Africans in Zambia, 1925-64". MA Thesis, Milwaukee, Wisconsin

36. NAZ, Herbert Stanley to Sir Geoffrey Thomas, 5th April 1924, 19th May 1925, Lusaka.

37. NAZ/SEC 2/26 Northern Rhodesia Notice No. 21 of 1929.

38. Ndulo Muna (1987). *Mining Rights in Zambia*. Lusaka: Kenneth Kaunda Foundation.

39. Nevill Ralph (1911). *Floreat Etona: Anecdotes and Memories of Eton College*. London: Macmillan.

40. Nick Fraser (2006). *The Importance of Being Eton*. London: Short Books, June.

41. Northern Rhodesia,(1935). *Annual Report on the Social and Economic Progress of the People of Northern Rhodesia, 1934* London: His Majesty's Stationery Office.

42. Northern Rhodesia (1927). *Annual Report on the Social and Economic Progress of the People of Northern Rhodesia, 1925-26*. London: His Majesty's Stationery.

43. O'Callaghan Bryn (1997). *Understanding History: The World and Africa*. Windhoek: Longman.

44. Palmer Robin, "Land in Zambia," *Zambia Land and Labour Studies*, vol. 1, Occasional Paper No. 2, National Archives, Lusaka.

45. Patrick M. Mvunga,(1980). *The Colonial Foundations of Zambia's Land Tenure System*. Lusaka: NECZAM.

46. Perelman M.,(2001). "The Secret History of Primitive Accumulation and Classical Political Economy", In *The Commoner*, 2, pp. 1-22.

47. Phiri Bizeck J. (2001). "Colonial Legacy and the Role of Society in the Creation and Demise of Autocracy in Zambia, 1964-1991." *Nordic Journal of African Studies* 10(2), p.224.

48. Phiri Isaac (2001). *Proclaiming Political Pluralism: Churches and Political Transitions in Africa*. London: Praeger.

49. Ranger Terence (2004). 'Nationalist historiography, patriotic history and the history of the nation: the struggle over the past in Zimbabwe', *Journal of Southern African Studies*, 30 (2), pp. 215 – 234

50. Rupert Godfrey, ed., *Letters from a Prince: Edward, Prince of Wales to Mrs. Freda Dudley Ward. March 1919–January 1921*. London: Warner Books, 1998.

51. Sapire Hilary (2018). “The Prince and Afrikaners: The Royal Visit of 1925.” *Royal Studies Journal* 5(1), pp.110-11.

52. Simson Howard (1985). *Zambia: A Country Study*. Stockholm: Scandinavian Institute of African Studies.

53. Taiwo Olufemi (2010). *How Colonialism Preempted Modernity in Africa*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.

54. *The Times*, 6th June “Sir Herbert Stanley”, p.8. Retrieved on 8th August 2020.

55. *The Times*, 6th June, p.8.

56. Theo Aronson (1975). *Royal Ambassadors: British Royalties in Southern Africa, 1860-1947*. Cape Town: David Philip.

57. Tim Card (2001). *Eton Established: A History from 1440 to 1860*. London: John Murray.

58. Turnbull Joanna (2010). *Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary of Current English, Eighth Edition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

59. Two’, *Zambezia*, 15, 2 (1998), 123-146.

60. UNESCO (1964). *Education in Northern Rhodesia: Report and Recommendations Prepared by the UNESCO Planning Commission {The Radford Report}*. Lusaka: Government Printers.

61. Webster Linden Bradfield (1970). "Linden Bradfield Webster's Reminiscences of the Siege of Mafeking." *Military History Journal* 1(7). Retrieved on 3/02/2021.

62. West James E and Lamb Peter O. (1932). *He-who-sees-in-the Dark; The Boys' Story of Frederick Burnham, the American Scout* (New York: Boy Scouts of America).

63. Wood J. (2005). *So Far and No Further! Rhodesia's Bid for Independence During the Retreat from Empire*. London: Trafford Publishing.

64. Wright Martin,(1945). 'The Development of the Legislative Council 1606 – 1945' in Margerly Perham (Ed) *Studies in Colonial Legislatures*. London: Faber and Faber.